

Many of us fall at the very first hurdle...

When engaged in research as a career, either in academia, clinic, or industry, we tend to think that the hard part is getting funding or doing the actual research.

Many researchers view writing as a secondary skill. They have no idea of the inner workings of the scholarly publishing industry, or how their science is disseminated. Publishing research papers is a skill in itself.

Here, we explore the dreaded editorial desk checks.

Not all checks are the same. They flag issues with different severity levels. Some lead to outright rejection, and some can be fixed by small adjustments in text, or even the insertion of a sentence.

Let's start small.

1. Incomplete front matter

The beginning (or "title page") of a paper should always contain:

a. TITLE

I wrote a whole thing about titles [here](#).

There's a lot more to add, and this will happen shortly.

b. LIST OF CONTRIBUTING AUTHORS

Some publications ask for each author's highest academic degree.

I advise everyone to sign up for an [ORCID](#) account.

c. CORRESPONDING AUTHOR'S EMAIL

One person in the multiple author team is ultimately responsible for communicating with the target journal; this is the corresponding author, lead author, or senior author (at least in biomed papers).

Please see a great resource [here](#).

d. LIST OF KEYWORDS

If there are a couple of specific scientific terms that keep popping up in the answers to the main questions (why is the research important, what did you do, how did you do it), then they are your keywords.

e. CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

A conflict of interest is a situation in which an interest or connection—direct or indirect—could influence the research design or interpretation of the results obtained.

Authors and reviewers are expected to disclose and declare any potential for bias to the journal's editorial team.

➡ When the journal operates a [double anonymisation process](#), these are precisely the items that need to be removed before the manuscript package makes its way [to the reviewers](#) (along with other small edits to the main text).

Editorial desk checks are details that lead to complicated and protracted exchanges with the editorial staff, delaying publication of a paper.

After all the hard work, having to go through a submission process all over again because of formatting misses or forgotten statements is just frustrating.

Let's dive in part

2. Incomplete back matter.

This is not your main text and most publications exclude it from the formal word count.

These are must haves for clear understanding of the message of the paper and to build trust in the research process.

a. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

A research project starts with an original idea, and preliminary data is often needed to convince funders.

People that perform wet lab experiments, those that programme and code software, those that source the funding, and those that review the final paper all have important and distinct roles.

See all 14 types of contributor roles [here](#).

b. TABLE TITLES AND FIGURE CAPTIONS

These are essential for clarity.

Table titles should always make clear what the table displays and main relationships under comparison.

Figure legends should expand all abbreviations, symbols used, and scale bar size, as well as mention every component panel. Read more [here](#).

c. REFERENCES

This pertains not just to the list at the end, where all the sources are cited, but also the in-text citations.

Invest time and resources on learning about the different formatting requirements.

Let the software (Zotero is free) do the work for you, but double-check all citations.

d. DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Sometimes, bad actors infiltrate the publishing landscape.

They are getting better, but one thing they still can't do is convince everyone at once.

When data, protocols, and materials are available from different repositories, your findings are more easily replicated and your research trusted and cited. Discover more [here](#).

e. FUNDING INFORMATION

Not all research in the life sciences is expensive, but most tends to be.

PhD students and postdocs require money to pay for the equipment and materials they use, apart from their own salaries and stipends.

Funding bodies (international institutions, local governments, independent charities) need to be acknowledged in this section.

Recent initiatives regarding a registry for funders have started. For instance, [here](#).

 These are the trust markers intrinsic to the study.

Having explored the front and back matter of research papers, the heart of the subject is summarised [here](#).

3. Main checks

These are the non-negotiables that stop publication of a paper in its tracks. Cause for expressions of concern. Responsible for [audits](#) and [retractions](#).

a. MATCHING DATA TO METHODS

Data collection described in the methods section should match the tables and figures in the results section. Cite them all consecutively in the order they are presented in the text. The data illustrated in figures and tables must be interpreted accurately in the text—are any discrepancies apparent?

b. PUBLICATION SCOPE

The research must be relevant to the journal's audience. The main subject area could be very targeted (The Journal of Physiology) or a generalist publication (Science magazine). Even preprint repositories can specialize and cater to a particular “flavour” of scientist (SocArXiv or medRxiv).

c. ARTICLE TYPE

When submitting to a journal, formatting requirements are often divided by article type. A biology research article follows an IMRaD format. Reviews can be narrative, scoping, or focused; however, meta-analysis or systematic are highly structured. Some journals may accept case reports or editorials.

Please follow the requirements for the suitable article type and do not waste your time submitting to a journal that does not accept that format.

d. PLAGIARISM CHECK

Using detection software is standard for most publishers.

A similarity index score within acceptable limits is <15%. Any single-source overlap of >10% is considered very concerning and will lead to a desk rejection in most cases.

Rewriting and paraphrasing are essential to solve plagiarism issues.

e. ETHICAL APPROVAL

Clinical and preclinical trials require Institutional Review Board or Ethics Committee approval prior to being conducted.

Additionally, a study with human subjects should include a statement of informed consent to participate; separate consent to publish individual identifiable details is required also.

To recap:

Once your manuscript

- ✓ Is appropriately identified in the title page,
 - ✓ Passes integrity checks and is aligned with scope,
 - ✓ Contains back matter that matches the manuscript contents,
- there should be no reason for a **desk rejection**.